

Extraction Records: Technology Acceptance and Use Models

A Decision Framework for Selecting Technology Acceptance and Use Models: TAM, TAM2, TAM3, UTAUT, and UTAUT2

Anonymized for peer review

Each record below registers six elements systematically extracted from the primary source of each model: core constructs and definitions, proposed causal relationships, moderating variables, original application context, assumed type of use, and primary adoption stage.

The extraction followed a structured protocol grounded in concept-centric review procedures (Webster & Watson, 2002), treating the foundational articles as units of analysis. Construct definitions were preserved as closely as possible to the original wording to ensure terminological traceability. These records constitute Component 1 of the framework and the **analytical basis** from which the analytical dimensions (D1–D5), the guiding inquiries (Supplementary Material C2), and the descriptive profiles (Supplementary Material C3) were subsequently derived.

Extraction Record: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Primary reference: Davis (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. MIS Quarterly, 13(3), 319–340.

Extraction Element	Recorded Content
Core constructs and definitions	Perceived Usefulness (PU): the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance their job performance. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU): the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort.
Proposed causal relationships	PEOU → PU → Behavioral Intention → Actual System Use. PEOU has a direct effect on PU. Both PU and PEOU influence behavioral intention, which in turn determines actual use. The attitude construct was removed in later versions due to its marginal predictive value.
Moderating variables	Not emphasized in the original formulation. The model assumes that all external variable effects operate entirely through PU and PEOU, with no explicit moderation.
Original application context	Information systems in organizational settings. Originally validated with office software (word processors) in a corporate context.
Assumed type of use	Voluntary or mandatory use, without explicit distinction between the two regimes in the original formulation. The model does not

	operationalize the difference between imposed and freely chosen adoption.
Primary adoption stage	Initial acceptance. The model focuses on the formation of behavioral intention prior to or shortly after first contact with the technology.

Extraction Record: Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2)

Primary reference: Venkatesh and Davis (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. Management Science, 46(2), 186–204.

Extraction Element	Recorded Content
Core constructs and definitions	Inherits TAM constructs (PU and PEOU). Adds social influence constructs: subjective norm (perception of important others' expectations), image (degree to which technology use is associated with social status). Adds cognitive instrumental processes: job relevance, output quality, result demonstrability.
Proposed causal relationships	Subjective norm → PU (via internalization and identification). Subjective norm → Behavioral intention (via compliance, in mandatory settings only). Image → PU. Job relevance → PU. Output quality → PU. Result demonstrability → PU. PU → Behavioral intention. PEOU → PU. PEOU → Behavioral intention.
Moderating variables	Experience and voluntariness of use. Voluntariness moderates the effect of subjective norm on intention: the direct effect of subjective norm on intention is significant only in mandatory use contexts. Experience moderates the effect of subjective norm over time, weakening it as familiarity increases.
Original application context	Organizational and work-related contexts. Validated across four organizations with three longitudinal measurement points, covering both voluntary (studies 1 and 2) and mandatory use (studies 3 and 4).
Assumed type of use	Explicitly distinguishes voluntary and mandatory use. Voluntariness is operationalized as a moderating variable, and the model tests distinct hypotheses for each use regime.
Privileged adoption stage	Initial acceptance. Validated at three time points, but the focus remains on the formation of behavioral intention during early stages of adoption.

Extraction Record: Technology Acceptance Model 3 (TAM3)

Primary reference: Venkatesh and Bala (2008). Technology Acceptance Model 3 and a research agenda on interventions. Decision Sciences, 39(2), 273–315.

Extraction Element	Recorded Content
Core constructs and definitions	Integrates TAM2 constructs. Adds antecedents of PEOU organized through an anchoring-and-adjustment logic. Anchors (stable initial beliefs): computer self-efficacy (belief in one's ability to use the system), perceptions of external control (belief that organizational and technical resources exist to support use),

	computer anxiety (degree of apprehension when using computers), computer playfulness (degree of cognitive spontaneity in interactions with computers). Adjustments (experience-dependent perceptions): perceived enjoyment and objective usability.
Proposed causal relationships	Anchor antecedents → PEOU. Adjustment antecedents → PEOU. PEOU → PU (inherited from TAM/TAM2). PU → Behavioral intention. PEOU → Behavioral intention. Behavioral intention → Actual use. The model retains the TAM2 relational structure and adds PEOU antecedents without proposing cross-effects between PU and PEOU determinants.
Moderating variables	Experience, as a variable that moderates the strength of relationships between antecedents and use perceptions over time. As experience increases, the effects of anxiety and self-efficacy on PEOU tend to diminish.
Original application context	Organizational contexts requiring detailed understanding of use barriers and conditions of interaction with the technology. The model was designed to guide practical interventions such as training, technical support, and system design, making it suitable when the researcher needs to diagnose specific levers of adoption.
Assumed type of use	Voluntary or mandatory use, with less emphasis on distinguishing between use regimes than on the variation of antecedents as a function of accumulated experience.
Privileged adoption stage	Acceptance and variations in use perceptions as experience accumulates. The model examines how user perceptions change with experience, making it appropriate for longitudinal investigations or studies following users at different stages of technology familiarity.

Extraction Record: Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

Primary reference: Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, and Davis (2003). *User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view*. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(3), 425–478.

Extraction Element	Recorded Content
Core constructs and definitions	Performance expectancy: the degree to which an individual believes that using the system will help them attain gains in job performance. Effort expectancy: the degree of ease associated with the use of the system. Social influence: the degree to which an individual perceives that important others believe they should use the new system. Facilitating conditions: the degree to which an individual believes that an organizational and technical infrastructure exists to support use of the system.
Proposed causal relationships	Performance expectancy → Behavioral intention. Effort expectancy → Behavioral intention. Social influence → Behavioral intention. Facilitating conditions → Use behavior (without

	mediation by intention when effort expectancy is in the model). Behavioral intention → Use behavior.
Moderating variables	Gender, age, experience, and voluntariness of use. Each moderator acts on specific relationships: performance expectancy is stronger for men and younger workers; effort expectancy is more significant for women and older, less experienced workers; social influence is contingent on all four moderators; the effect of facilitating conditions on use is moderated by age and experience.
Original application context	Organizational contexts, especially those associated with job performance. Validated across four organizations with three longitudinal measurement points, covering both voluntary and mandatory use.
Assumed type of use	Both voluntary and mandatory, with voluntariness of use operationalized as a moderating variable. The model was developed and validated in organizational settings where the distinction between free and imposed use is analytically relevant.
Privileged adoption stage	Acceptance and use. The model articulates intention formation with the explanation of actual use behavior, including moderators that capture variation over time and across user profiles.

Extraction Record: Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2)

Primary reference: Venkatesh, Thong, and Xu (2012). Consumer acceptance and use of information technology: Extending the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. MIS Quarterly, 36(1), 157–178.

Extraction Element	Recorded Content
Core constructs and definitions	Inherits the four UTAUT constructs. Adds: hedonic motivation (the fun or pleasure derived from using technology), price value (consumers' cognitive tradeoff between the perceived benefits of the applications and the monetary cost for using them), habit (the extent to which people tend to perform behaviors automatically because of learning).
Proposed causal relationships	Performance expectancy → Behavioral intention. Effort expectancy → Behavioral intention. Social influence → Behavioral intention. Facilitating conditions → Behavioral intention and Use behavior. Hedonic motivation → Behavioral intention. Price value → Behavioral intention. Habit → Behavioral intention and Use behavior. Behavioral intention → Use behavior. The effect of behavioral intention on use decreases with increasing experience.
Moderating variables	Gender, age, and experience. Voluntariness of use was removed as it is considered an intrinsic characteristic of the voluntary consumer context. Moderators act on the relationships between constructs and behavioral intention, with distinct patterns for each additional construct.
Original application context	Individual consumer contexts and voluntary use. Validated with 1,512 mobile Internet consumers in Hong Kong, at two time points (four-month interval). The model was explicitly developed to

	extend UTAUT to the consumer context, where hedonic motivation and perceived value are relevant determinants.
Assumed type of use	Predominantly voluntary. The model presupposes that adoption occurs by individual choice, without organizational imposition, which structurally differentiates its scope from the original UTAUT.
Privileged adoption stage	Acceptance, use, and continuance. The incorporation of habit allows the model to address not only initial adoption but also consolidated use behavior, making it appropriate for investigations covering users at different stages of technology experience.